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NEW ASPECTS OF USING ELEMENTS WITH ABNORMAL PHOTOVOLTAIC VOLTAGES

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Abstract: *In this paper, the results of experimental studies of the AFN effect are carried out and its theory is developed. The nature of microprocesses leading to the occurrence of anomalously high photoelectric voltages (AHV effect) is formulated and determined. The energy parameters of the AHV films were studied.*

Keywords: *anomalous photovoltage (AHV), current-voltage characteristics, lux-volt characteristics, photovoltage spectra.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, developers in the fields of microelectronics and semiconductors have placed significant emphasis on investigating the phenomenon of anomalous photovoltage. This research aims to create unique optoelectronic devices for measurement and conversion techniques [1-9]. Scientific studies have revealed that when films made from various semiconductor materials are illuminated using a special technology, they generate photovoltaic voltages on the order of several thousand volts (anomalous photovoltage effect). The spectral sensitivity range of these semiconductor materials is quite broad, extending from the visible to the infrared spectrum.

Therefore, the study of photoelectric effects and the modification of technology to obtain thin-film structures with the anomalous photovoltaic voltage effect (APV) are relevant issues in modern

semiconductor physics. To achieve the set goal, targeted research should be conducted in the following directions:

Improving the technology for obtaining elements with anomalous photovoltage from semiconductor structures, including superlattice structures.

Controlling output parameters and reproducibility of the photosensitivity of the investigated samples.

Conducting experimental work to study the influence of isovalent impurities and external conditions on the anomalous photovoltage effect.

Investigating the influence of polarized light on the manifestation of anomalous photovoltage in a magnetic field.

In this regard, a series of scientific studies have been conducted. For instance, in the work [11], a hierarchy of the development of anomalously high photoelectric voltages in semiconductor films with a specific deposition angle is presented. Work [12] investigates anomalously high photon voltages in terbium molybdate, while work [13] outlines the results of studying the transition surface photo-voltage of the P-type in more complex structures of Cu_3BiS_3 . The role of radiative and non-radiative relaxation processes in generating light from silicon is justified in the work [14].

In our Republic, in the direction of obtaining thin films with anomalous photovoltages, the works of scientists under the guidance of E.I. Adirovich should be noted. They obtained germanium films and studied their properties. Film deposition with a thickness of $0.1 \mu\text{m}$ was carried out at an angle of 45-60 degrees at a substrate temperature of 200-400°C. At room temperature, APV values were 100 V. Currently, Professor S. Otajonov is conducting research on new aspects of applying APV films based on cadmium sulfide [15].

Despite the extensive study of APV elements, questions regarding the photoelectric, photomagnetic, magneto-optical, and other properties of films with the effect of anomalous photovoltaic voltage remain unexplored.

2. Research Methodology

The technological regime for obtaining APV films depends on a large number of parameters, such as the evaporator and substrate temperatures, deposition angle, film thickness, composition, and pressure of residual gases in the vacuum chamber, as well as the conditions of thermal treatment after deposition. Each semiconductor material corresponds to its optimal regime, and even small deviations, even in a single parameter, can lead to the disappearance of the APV effect in the produced films. Therefore, developing the technology for obtaining APV films from a specific material requires extensive experimental work, numerous trial depositions with sequential variation of several technological parameters, their combinations, and finding parameters specific to achieving the APV effect in films of that particular semiconductor material.

The APV effect has also been studied in films and crystals obtained by doping with isovalent impurities and exhibiting double refraction. For this purpose, a special methodology and setup for

obtaining APV films from various semiconductor materials have been developed and described in [7]. The developed methodology and the corresponding setup ensure heterogeneity in the structure and composition of the film. When illuminating a non-uniform polycrystalline semiconductor, a photo-EMF ventilation can occur at barriers of different types. For example, films of CdTe, CdSe, ZnS, etc., exhibit the so-called APV effect, characterized by the emergence of anomalously high photovoltages exceeding the bandgap width of the corresponding semiconductor. It turns out that the APV film represents a complex superlattice (SMS) system, consisting of a large number of microphotoelements ($\sim 10^5$ cm⁻¹ and more), each of which is associated with some structural feature of the film, such as micro-roughness, the presence of intercrystalline layers or grains, block boundaries, etc. In addition to the ventilatory photo-EMF, the effect may be due to diffusion (Debye) photo-EMF in the volume of a microcrystal. In heterogeneous SMS structures, the photo-EMF is predominantly determined by the intercrystalline substance. Polycrystalline and amorphous APV films (Sb₂S₃ и Sb₂Se₃) may have very high effective volumetric resistivity (for example, $\sim 10^{10}$ – 10^{11} Ohm•cm) and low carrier mobility due to the presence of crystalline inclusions in the amorphous phase, where microheterojunctions are localized [8].

As a result of the conducted studies, the APV effect was first discovered in copper-indium selenide and cadmium telluride with isovalent impurities (Cu, Ag, and Au), germanium and silicon (Al, Ga, and In), and in some equimolar compositions (PbSe Sb₂Se₃ или PbS Sb₂Se). Polished glass, ceramic, and ferroelectric plates were used as substrates. It was established that APV films are obtained only with oblique deposition on the substrate. A shutter, moved parallel to the surface of the source using an electromagnetic drive, was installed between the evaporator and the substrates in the vacuum chamber. By changing the speed of the shutter movement and the inclination of the substrate relative to the molecular beam axis, it was possible to independently control the angular anisotropy of deposition and the thickness gradient of the films, obtaining, in particular, films of constant thickness during inclined deposition and wedge-shaped films during normal deposition. Both types of films were obtained on all investigated semiconductor materials. From the experimental results, it follows that APV films are formed only in a homogeneous and anisotropic deposition, regardless of the presence or absence of a thickness gradient. Studies of the crystal structure showed that one of the factors leading to the APV effect is heterogeneity in structure and composition. Additionally, in APV films, the photodiffusion and photoelectric mechanisms are fulfilled as:

$$V_{\text{AФH}} = f(B, R_0),$$

where $V_{\text{AФH}}$ is the APV effect; B is the intensity of incident light; R_0 is the dark resistance of the film.

3. Results and Discussion

In order to determine the application area and technical possibilities of the APV effect, we conducted studies on the photoelectric, magneto-electric, and photoelectret properties of newly obtained APV films and APV elements based on ferroelectric materials [8]. Experimental and theoretical

investigations of volt-ampere characteristics (VAC), lux-volt characteristics (LVC), and spectral characteristics (SC) of APV films have been conducted [7].

Based on the model proposed in works [1-5] for the APV film of cadmium telluride and considering the complexity of the structure and heterogeneity in the structure and composition of other APV films, generalizing the results in [6], experimental and theoretical investigations of volt-ampere characteristics (VAC), lux-volt characteristics (LVC), and spectral characteristics (SC) of APV films have been conducted [7].

The results of the studies showed that the dark VAC is linear up to values of $E = 5 \times 10^3$ V/cm, and for stronger fields up to breakdown ($E = 5 \times 10^5$ V/cm), it becomes superlinear. The linear portion of the VAC at the origin depends on the degree of shunting of micro-p-n junctions. After the linear portion, the VAC has a superlinear region. However, according to the theory, when the effect of transferring injected carriers (α) occurs between forward-biased and reverse-biased p-n junctions, there should be another linear portion on the VAC after the superlinear region, which was not observed in the experiment. The physical meaning of the superlinearity of the VAC is that while the recombination losses of the injection current in the p-n regions constitute a small fraction of the saturation current of a single junction, almost all the voltage applied to the junctions falls on the emitters. At sufficiently high currents, the reverse-biased p-n junctions begin to play a major role, and the VAC becomes sublinear. No transition from the superlinear region to the sublinear region was observed in the experimental VAC.

Upon illumination of the samples, the VAC straightens, and at high light intensities, it becomes linear. The straightening of the VAC at high light intensities is presumably associated with a decrease in the differential resistance of reverse-biased junctions and a drop in voltage on the series resistance.

Another important characteristic of the anomalous photovoltage effect is the lux-volt characteristics (LVC), which have been studied in the work [7]. The results showed that the lux-volt characteristics of chalcogenides at room temperature are linear up to light intensities of $V = 0.35$ W/cm². At liquid nitrogen temperatures, linearity is maintained only for excitation intensities $V < 2 \times 10^{-2}$ W/cm². Importantly, at 770 K, the photovoltage sharply increases in the region of small light intensities, and already at $V = 10^{-6}$ W/cm², it reaches values of about 1 V. Further increasing the excitation intensity leads to the growth of anomalous photovoltage up to several tens of thousands of volts, and saturation is not observed until $V = 0.35$ W/cm².

In addition to LVC, spectral dependencies with a sign inversion of the photovoltage are observed in films of various substances (Figure 1). Measurement results of the spectra of anomalous photovoltage in CdTe, Si, Ge, GaAs, Se, GaP, and chalcogenide alloys showed that the APV effect is induced by light from the region of intrinsic absorption. As part of spectral studies, polar diagrams were obtained (dependence of photovoltage on the angle of illumination of APV films with monochromatic light), providing a clear determination of the origin of the APV in microphotoelements.

Fig. 1. Typical spectra of photovoltage in APV films: Si, Se, CdAs, Ge, CdP, CdTe; Absence of sign inversion on polar diagrams allows for a clear conclusion about the photovoltaic (p-n junction) mechanism of the APV effect. If there is inversion in the region of short monochromatic waves (near the angle of film deposition) on polar diagrams, then we are talking about the diffusion (Demer's) mechanism of the effect.

Thus, the combination of polar (angular) and spectral measurements provides a clear answer to the question of the nature of microphotoelements in APV films.

Conclusion

An anomalously large photoelectric effect in semiconductor films doped with isovalent impurities has been developed and studied.

Using the electro-optical and magneto-optical properties of APV elements, optoelectronic voltage transformers (OVT) and current transformers (OCT) are developed. Optoelectronic voltage transformers have a transformation coefficient of about 1000. APV elements can serve as primary transducers for various types of information, such as electrical, optical, and non-electrical quantities. Therefore, APV elements can act as sources of large electrostatic fields.

Based on the results of the research (VAC, LVC, SC, and electromagnetic measurements), all necessary characteristic parameters and values can be determined for the development of new optoelectronic devices for monitoring and measuring specific parameters based on the anomalous photovoltage effect.

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